

Spectroscopic Study of the Interaction of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Ions with Amino Acids in Aqueous Solution

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Manuscript received 18 January 1996, revised 19 August 1996, accepted 8 November 1996

The interaction of amino acids with metal ions plays an important role in the reactivity and properties of protein¹. Many workers²⁻⁷ tried to resolve the nature of coordination of α -amino acids in complexes of the first series of transition metal ions and concluded that in the complexes the amino acids exist as zwitterion being coordinated through the carboxylate group.

When an amino acid is added to an aqueous solution of the metal ion, the water molecule from the coordination sphere is replaced by the amino acid molecule. Though the stepwise formation of the complex predicts⁸ the formation of several complexes of the type $[M(H_2O)_{6-n}L_n]^{2+}$ (where $n = 1, 2, 3$, etc.) yet the presence of mono-, bis- and tris-complexes have only been reported^{3,9}. Ozutsumi and Ohtaki⁹ showed that the bis- and tris-glycinato complexes of copper(II) are formed when the ratio of $C_{gly}/C_{Cu^{2+}} > 13.7$.

Different methods have been used to study such interactions but the interaction of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) ions with aminoacids in aqueous solutions have not yet been studied by visible spectrophotometric method. Here, the interactions have been studied by this method and the equilibrium constants of the replacement processes along with the change of free energies have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The spectral change due to ligand exchange has been observed at 19 600 and 25 300 cm^{-1} respectively for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} ions, because the intensities of the bands are comparatively high. When amino acids are added, the peaks blue-shifted, the shift in the case of Ni^{II} ion being more prominent. Molar concentrations have been used to calculate the equilibrium constants of the replacement processes (Table 1).

There are evidences^{2,5-7,10} that in solution amino acids exist mainly as zwitterion especially at $pH < 7$, though the presence of bidentate amino acid anion can not be ignored. So, in the complexation of amino acid with the divalent metal ion, the major species is ML^{2+} , where zwitterion is coordinated through the carboxylate group^{2,5-7}. Of course, the presence of significant amount of ML^+ (where amino acid is a bidentate ligand) is also to be considered¹⁰. The stability constant of the bidentate complex ML^+ as reported¹⁰ is about a factor of 10^2 times larger than that of

the monodentate complex, ML^{2+} , although the ratio $[L^-]/[L^{\pm}]$ is only 10^{-2} in neutral solution. Therefore, the values of the equilibrium constants found in the present experiment will be neither of ML^{2+} nor of ML^+ but may be the average value of both the complexes as suggested by Led¹⁰.

TABLE I—THE EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF THE LIGAND REPLACEMENT

Compd	Ligands	ϵ_1	$\log K_1$	$-\Delta G$ (kcal) at 25°
Cobalt(II) nitrate	Glycine	5 80 \pm 0 09	2 56 \pm 0 02	3 50 \pm 0 02
	Alanine	5 96 \pm 0.06	2 34 \pm 0 02	3 19 \pm 0 02
	Valine	6 13 \pm 0 08	3 30 \pm 0 01	3 14 \pm 0 01
Cobalt(II) chloride	Glycine	6 01 \pm 0 06	2 43 \pm 0 02	3 31 \pm 0 02
	Alanine	6 09 \pm 0 09	2 28 \pm 0 02	3 11 \pm 0 03
	Valine	6 06 \pm 0 05	2 26 \pm 0 02	3 08 \pm 0 02
Nickel(II) nitrate	Glycine	5 62 \pm 0 02	2 63 \pm 0 01	3 59 \pm 0 02
	Alanine	5.99 \pm 0 04	2 46 \pm 0 01	3 36 \pm 0 02
	Valine	5 72 \pm 0 02	2 35 \pm 0 01	3 22 \pm 0 01
Nickel(II) chloride	Glycine	5 55 \pm 0 02	2 45 \pm 0 02	3 35 \pm 0 02
	Alanine	5 46 \pm 0 02	2 35 \pm 0 01	3 21 \pm 0 02
	Valine	5 63 \pm 0 02	2 32 \pm 0 01	3 17 \pm 0 01

The order of stability of complex formation¹¹ between the two metal ions is $Ni^{II} > Co^{II}$. In the present study the same trend has been observed. It has also been observed¹¹ that the stability constant for a particular metal ion complexed with amino acid is of the order : glycine > alanine. According to our results, the order can be extended as glycine > alanine > valine. Similar variation in the stability constant has also been reported earlier⁵.

The change of free energies of the ligand exchange processes have been calculated from the values of equilibrium constant. For both the metal ions, the variation of the change of free energy follows the sequence : glycine < alanine < valine, signifying that glycine can most easily replace water molecule from the coordination sphere of the metal ion and valine being a bulky molecule, perhaps displaces water molecule with difficulty.

Experimental

Cobalt(II) chloride (Chempol, G.R.) and cobalt(II) nitrate (AnalaR) were used as such. Nickel(II) chloride and nickel(II) nitrate were repeatedly recrystallised from double-distilled water. Aqueous solutions of the compounds were

prepared in triple-distilled water and standardised¹². Glycine (Sisco), L(+)-alanine (Merck) and L(+)-valine (Loba-Chemie) were used as such.

The compounds were heated at 110–120° for 5 h, just before preparing the solution with triple-distilled water. Spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer at 25°.

The concentrations of the aminoacids were kept as low as possible. Based on the report of Ozutsumi and Ohtaki⁹, it was assumed that only one molecule of water from the coordination sphere of the metal ion has been replaced by the amino acid molecule. The replacement process can be represented as

where L stands for the monodentate amino acid. The equilibrium constant was evaluated from the linearised equation^{6,13},

$$\frac{1}{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_0} \cdot \frac{[H_2O]}{K_1[L]} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_0}$$

where ε is the apparent extinction coefficient of the sample solution and ε_0 and ε_1 are those of $[M(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$ and $[M(H_2O)_5L]^{2+}$ respectively, $[H_2O]$ and $[L]$ are the concentrations of free solvent and free amino acid. The method of evaluation of the equilibrium constant has already been discussed in earlier study¹⁴.

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